

NZ·IS 3

New Zealand Hydrogen Symposium

Proceedings

3-5 February 2025

Te Whare Wānanga o Waitaha, Ōtautahi, Aotearoa
University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand

Caption: With over 150 participants from academia, industry, agencies, and governments across six continents, NZHS-3 was a powerful platform for hydrogen science and innovation.

NZHS-3 ORGANISING COMMITTEE:

Chairs: Rebecca Peer and Jannik Haas

Event organizers: Francisco Astorga Mendoza and Akash Handique

Local committee: Matt Watson, Andy Nicol, Aaron Marshall, Hamish Avery, David Dempsey

Contact: NZHS2025@canterbury.ac.nz

NZHS SERIES PLANNING COMMITTEE: Aaron Marshall (University of Canterbury), Anna Garden (University of Otago), Fei Yang (University of Waikato), Geoff Waterhouse (University of Auckland), Ludmila Adam (University of Auckland), Jannik Haas (University of Canterbury), John Kennedy (GNS Science), Jonathan Kitchen (Auckland University of Technology), Jonathan Leaver (Unitec), Kēpa Morgan (Mauri Model), Luke Liu (Victoria University of Wellington), Suren Wijeyekoon (Scion), Rebecca Peer (University of Canterbury), Robert Holt (Callaghan Innovation), Sally Brooker (University of Otago), Simon Kelly (Lincoln Agritech).

Keynote presentations

Prof Mike Stevens (Director, Ngāi Tahu Research Centre) [Link](#)
He Honoka Hou, He Āhua Tahwito Ngāi Tahu and New Energy in a Global World.

Prof Sven Teske (UTS, Australia) [Link](#)
Net-Zero emission targets and the role of hydrogen for the energy transition.

Prof André Cabrera Serrenho (Cambridge, UK) [Link](#)
The role of hydrogen in climate change mitigation.

Prof Peter Strasser (TU Berlin, Germany)
Electrocatalytic materials, interfaces, and devices for green hydrogen.

Prof Christian Breyer (LUT, Finland) [Link](#)
Global energy transition – Power-to-X economy will be built on renewable electricity and green hydrogen.

Dr Hans Christian Gils (German Aerospace Centre, Germany) [Link](#)
Development of the trans-European hydrogen network: model-based planning and status of implementation.

Prof Lianzhou Wang (University of Queensland) [Link](#)
Photoelectrode design for solar hydrogen and valuable chemical production.

Dr Carola Kantz (Mech. Eng. Industry Assoc. VDMA, Germany) [Link](#)
Industry challenges for hydrogen development.

Dr Claudio Pistidda (Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon, Germany)
The development of sustainable, high-performance hydrogen storage materials is underway.

Dr Hamish Miller (National Research Council, Italy) [Link](#)
Development of Sustainable Catalysts for production of H₂ and liquid e-fuels.

Prof Rodrigo Palma (Solar Energy Research Centre, Chile) [Link](#)
Power-to-X value chain: grid and decentralised perspectives in Chile.

Prof Pierluigi Mancarella (University of Melbourne, Australia) [Link](#)
Modelling and assessment of integrated electricity-gas-hydrogen energy infrastructure for net zero.

Prof Rangan Banerjee (Director IIT Delhi, India) [Link](#)
Green hydrogen: status and role in India's net zero future.

Invited Speaker Presentations

Saurabh Sinha (Executive Dean, Engineering UC).

Phil Mauger (Mayor of Christchurch).

Christian Stertz (Head of Department, Cooperation with Asia and Oceania, Federal Ministry of Education and Research, Germany).

Impulse talks: Gareth Wishart (H.W. Richardson) [Link](#), Nicoletta Moss (Hiringa Energy) [Link](#), Thomas Ritchie (Hardie Pacific) [Link](#), Christina Houlihan (BSPKL) [Link](#), and Linda Wright (NZ Hydrogen Council) [Link](#).

Industry panel: Linda Wright (NZ Hydrogen Council), André Cabrera (Cambridge University), Gareth Wishart (HWR), Michael Lee (Coregas), Brendon Miller (Methanex), Nicoletta Moss (Hiringa). Chaired by Prof Matt Watson and Prof Sally Brooker.

Anne Blumenthal (DAAD representative, New Zealand) [Link](#)
Funding opportunities to and from Germany.

Oral Presentations

Storage Session

Chairs: Prof Fei Yang and Dr Luke Liu

Prof Ian Wright (University of Canterbury) [Link](#)
Are “White” and “Orange” hydrogen viable alternatives to green hydrogen in Aotearoa New Zealand?

Dr Andrew Rowberg (Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory)
Impact of Metal Alloying on Hydrogen Uptake through Ilmenite and its Reduction to TiFe.

Dr Jose Bellosta von Colbe (Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon) [Link](#)
Development and testing of a container-based hydrogen and heat storage system with ~4 tons of metal hydride: the HyCARE.

Jonas Meier (Fabrum) [Link](#)
Development of a commercial hydrogen reliquefier.

Archa Santhosh (Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon) [Link](#)
Influence of transition metal substituents on activation of TiFe for hydrogen storage.

Dr Runhua Feng (University of Auckland) [Link](#)
Laboratory study of hydrogen injection into depleted hydrocarbon reservoir of Taranaki basin, New Zealand.

Ebert Alvares (Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon) [Link](#)
Multi-Physics Modelling FeTi Metal-Hydride Hydrogenation Processes.

Energy Strategies Session

Chairs: Dr John Kennedy and A/Prof Jannik Haas

Dr John Kennedy (GNS)
GNS Science Green Hydrogen Technology Programme.

Dr Marcos Pelenur (Energy Efficiency & Conservation Authority) [Link](#)
The Energy Efficiency and Conservation Authority (EECA) and Hydrogen.

Pablo Apablaza (University of Melbourne) [Link](#)
Future electricity and H₂ systems: Long-duration storage options for Australia.

A/Prof Jannik Haas, Rafaella Canessa (University of Canterbury) [Link](#)
Green hydrogen energy transitions New Zealand.

Production Session

Chairs: Prof Aaron Marshall and Dr Vedran Jovic

Dr Yan-Gu Lin (National Synchrotron Radiation Research C., Taiwan) [Link](#)
In-situ synchrotron X-ray techniques for probing restructuring dynamics of surface species in nanocatalysts.

Prof Jen Tien-Chien (University of Johannesburg) [Link](#)
Metal-decorated boron carbide for ultrahigh hydrogen storage: A Promising Approach to Advanced Energy Solutions.

Dr Anna Garden (University of Otago) [Link](#)
Design principles derived from calculations for tuning the hydrogen evolution activity of MoS₂ electrocatalysts.

Dr Siriluck Tesana (GNS Science) [Link](#)
Are transition metal (oxy)nitrides active catalysts for electrochemical nitrogen reduction?

Cross-cutting Topics Session

Chairs: Dr Selena Sheng and Dr Michelle Cook

Dr Jim Hinkley (IEA Hydrogen TCP) [Link](#)

Engaging with International Energy Agency hydrogen technology collaboration programme to accelerate NZ hydrogen research.

Dr Courtney Milner (Agilent Technologies, Australia) [Link](#)
Requirements and challenges of testing hydrogen.

Energy Systems Modelling Session

Chairs: Dr Michael Jack and Dr Rebecca Peer

Prof Andy Philpott (University of Auckland) [Link](#)
Electricity dispatch and pricing using agent decision rules.

Dr Arjan Abeynaike (University of Otago) [Link](#)
Fuel cell vs battery electric trucks: energy consumption on long-distance routes in Aotearoa.

Prof Andrea Raith (University of Auckland) [Link](#)
Hydrogen Production and Storage Optimisation in New Zealand.

Dr Michelle Cook (GNS) [Link](#)
Can green hydrogen increase the energy independence and resilience of rural and remote Marae?

Risk, Environmental and Social Dimensions

Chairs: Prof Janet Stephenson and Dr Rebecca Peer

Alice Bennett (University of Cambridge) [Link](#)
Can imported green hydrogen align with climate targets? Which end-uses are most beneficial?

Dr Mahnaz Shafiei (Swinburne University of Technology, Australia) [Link](#)
Innovative hydrogen gas sensors employing hybrid nanomaterials.

Dr Andrew Dickson (University Otago)
Green hydrogen in Aotearoa New Zealand: Insights into public attitudes.

Dr Rebecca Peer, Francisco Astorga-Mendoza (University of Canterbury) [Link](#)
Environmental, economic, and social trade-offs of a net-zero emissions energy system in New Zealand.

Posters

Kai Sellschopp, Thomas Klassen, Paul Jerabek, Claudio Pistidda
Accurate representation of hydrogen in metals by machine-learning enhanced

modelling of nuclear quantum effects.

Juergen Auster, Stephan Guenzel, Andreas Kriegsmann
Empirical correlation between relative total deformation and residual burst pressure after impact load tests on H₂ pressure vessels (Type VI).

Alexander Haack, Claudio Pistidda, Nigel Lucas
Mechanochemical reduction of New Zealand resources to TiFe for hydrogen storage.

Stella Steidl, Jannik Haas, Alaa Alhamwi, Rebecca Peer, Alejandro Zabala Figueroa, Wided Medjroubi
Optimizing Green Hydrogen Integration in Urban Energy Systems: A GIS-Based Comparative Study of New Zealand and German Cities.

Daniel Jia Sheng Chong, Timothy Walmsley, Michael Walmsley, Martin Atkins
Modelling Aotearoa-New Zealand's Green Energy Future: A P-Graph Approach to Achieving Renewable Self-Sufficiency and Hydrogen Export Potential.

Mohammad Zarar Rasheed, Chris Bumby, Karl Dahm, Peng Cao, Alexander Haack, Claudio Pistidda
Synthesis of TiFe alloy for hydrogen storage applications by direct calciothermic reduction of ilmenite sand.

Lukas Knorr, Nils Horstmann, Henning Meschede
From Surplus to Solution: Green Hydrogen's Role in Paderborn's Energy Transition.

Vicente Sepúlveda-Figueroa, Rodrigo Palma-Behnke
Power-to-X opportunities and challenges for the energy transition in Latin America.

Ho-Ryong Park, Beom-Jun Kim, Su-Jin Ryu, Hyun-Seog Roh
Customized Ni-MgO-ZrO₂ Catalysts for Hydrogen Production via Dry Reforming of Methane Using Coke Oven Gas: Optimizing the MgO Content.

Ebert Alvares, Kai Sellschopp, Bo Wang, Shing Young Kang, Brandon Wood, Thomas Klassen, Tae Wook Heo, Paul Jerabek, Claudio Pistidda
Multi-Physics Modelling FeTi Metal-Hydride Hydrogenation Processes.

Kayla Prendergast, Anna Garden, Chris Mills
A Computational Investigation into Hydrogen Production on Twisted Molybdenum Disulfide.

Laura Titheridge, Aaron Marshall
Comparative Analysis of In-Plane and Through-Plane Conductivity in Commercial Anion Exchange Membranes for Water Electrolysis Applications.

Alhasan Ali Abdulwahid, Jonathan Leaver, Ehsan Shafiei, Michael Jack
Simulating Consumer Behaviour Towards Hydrogen Heavy Vehicles.

Gerrit Green, Fenya Pflaeging, Christian Töbermann
Operating Strategies for Electrolyzers Coupled to Wind Turbines: Optimizing
Hydrogen Production and Reducing Grid Stress.

Nicholas Smith, Anna Garden
Computation Modelling of the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction on Asymmetric Cu
Nanoparticles.

Bastien Gelin, Richard Adams, Jason Bartlett
Australasia's first industrial-scale hydrogen testing facility.

Michael Bennington, Michael Bennington, Varinder Singh, Aaron Marshall, Sally
Brooker
Development of a NZ setup for testing homogeneous photocatalytic hydrogen
production, and results obtained for some catalysts.

Varinder Singh, Harry Cahyanto, Alex Yip, Sally Brooker
Ethylenediamine-promoted High Dispersion of Low %Pd on Silica Support
Results in High and Robust Catalytic Activity.

Yutao Zhai, John Kennedy, Fei Yang
Microstructural Evolution and Hydrogen Storage Behavior of Ti-V-Cr-Mn-Fe High-
Entropy Alloys Synthesized via Mechanical Alloying.

Hadi Vatankhah Ghadim, Rebecca Peer, Jannik Haas, Grant Read
A Trans-Tasman Subsea HVDC interconnection: An Alternative for Hydrogen as
an Electricity Buffer.

Simon Stuber, Hadi Vatankhah Ghadim, Rebecca Peer, Jannik Haas, Grant
Read
Forecasting Renewable Jet Fuel Demand in New Zealand: Understanding
Required Green Hydrogen Under Different Scenarios.

Lekshmi Dinachandran, Ebert Alvares, Paul Jerabek, Anna Garden
Investigating the Impact of Silicon Impurities on Hydrogen Storage in TiFe Alloys:
A CALPHAD and DFT Approach.

Luke McIntosh, Chris Hann, Dennis Chapman, Alan Chapman, Steve Canny
Hydrogen Energy Storage Investigation.

Jinjiang Liu, David Dempsey, Andy Nicol, Matt Parker
Numerical study of the impacts of interlayers on the performance of underground
hydrogen storage.

Kieran DeMonte, Aaron Marshall, Sally Brooker
Immobilized Molecular Catalysts for Heterogeneous Electrochemical Hydrogen Evolution (HER) and CO₂ Reduction (CO₂RR).

Qiu hao Chang, David Dempsey
Applications of Molecular Dynamics Simulation in Underground Hydrogen Storage.

Pablo Apablaza, Ronggen Chen, Sleiman Mhanna, Pierluigi Mancarella
Planning Under Uncertainty of Integrated Electricity-Hydrogen Systems: An Australian Case Study.

Ronggen Chen, Sleiman Mhanna, Pierluigi Mancarella
Joint Multi-stage Planning of Electricity and Hydrogen Systems: An Australian case study.

Baxter Williams, Robert Hooper, Geoffrey Chase
Modelling residential energy use: Presentation and validation of an agent-based approach.

Karan Titus, David Dempsey, Rebecca Peer, Jannik Haas
Transitioning Aotearoa New Zealand's future geothermal from baseload to flexible dispatch via Green Hydrogen.

Akash Handique, Jannik Haas, Rebecca Peer
100% Renewable Electricity Transition Pathways for the Pacific Islands.

Maddison Zegeer, Jannik Haas, Rebecca Peer, Andy Philpott, Grant Read
Implicit modelling of hydropower uncertainty in capacity expansion tools.

Edward Yates
Characterising faults and fractures in the onshore Taranaki basin for Underground Hydrogen Storage in depleted gas reservoirs.

Phillippe Bruneau, Dirk Pons, Patrick Shepherd, Alan Wood
Grid loading effects of a hydrogen production plant – A PyPSA model.

Shae Patel
Metal-Organic Frameworks for CO₂ Electrocatalysis.

Shang Jiang, Cong Quoc Tran, Mehdi Keyvan-Ekbatani
A multivariate diffusion model for predicting transportation energy demand: a New Zealand case study.

Flash talks

Chair: Leonardo Bolstad

Alexander Haack, Claudio Pistidda, Nigel Lucas
Mechanochemical reduction of New Zealand resources to TiFe for hydrogen storage.

Stella Steidl, Jannik Haas, Alaa Alhamwi, Rebecca Peer, Alejandro Zabala Figuerola, Wided Medjroubi
Optimizing Green Hydrogen Integration in Urban Energy Systems: A GIS-Based Comparative Study of New Zealand and German Cities.

Daniel Jia Sheng, Timothy Walmsley, Michael Walmsley, Martin Atkins
Modelling Aotearoa-New Zealand's Green Energy Future: A P-Graph Approach to Achieving Renewable Self-Sufficiency and Hydrogen Export Potential.

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Poster and Presentation Prizes

First-place student presentation

Lukas Knorr: *From Surplus to Solution: Green Hydrogen's Role in Paderborn's Energy Transition.*

Second-place student presentation

Madison Zegeer: *Implicit modelling of hydropower uncertainty in capacity expansion tools.*

Third-place student presentation

Kieran DeMonte: *Immobilized Molecular Catalysts for Heterogeneous Electrochemical Hydrogen Evolution (HER) and CO₂ Reduction (CO₂RR).*

Commended student presentation

Alexander Haack: *Mechanochemical reduction of New Zealand resources to TiFe for hydrogen storage.*

Varinder Singh: *Ethylenediamine-promoted High Dispersion of Low %Pd on Silica Support Results in High and Robust Catalytic Activity.*

Lekshmi Dinachandran: *Investigating the Impact of Silicon Impurities on Hydrogen Storage in TiFe Alloys: A CALPHAD and DFT Approach.*

Alice Bennett: *Can imported green hydrogen align with climate targets? Which end-uses are most beneficial?*

Student organisers

Akash Jyoti Handique and Francisco Astorga-Mendoza

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We thank our sponsors, whose generous support has made NZHS 2025 possible. Their commitment to advancing sustainable energy solutions is invaluable.

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